

COROB-X FIELD TEST WISDOM DATA

Lanzarote Field test campaign manip book – from 2023-01-29 to 2023-02-11

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OVERVIEW OF THE FIELD TEST SITE OF COROB-X AND MEASUREMENT PROFILES PERFORMED WITH WISDOM MOUNTED ON COYOTE

The name of the profiles are those of the corresponding folder containing the raw data

FREESPACE MEASUREMENTS

Perspectives : such measurements can be used to remove the wheels signature from the radargrams

6 meters profile with 10 cm and 15 cm diameters metallic spheres buried along the profile. The spheres are buried 10 to 15 cm deep (shallow)

The hyperbola (spheres signature on radargrams) are not easily visible, this can be due to the multiple reflections on the wheels. The first tens of cm seem to be shaded by the wheels pattern.

PROFILE_BEFORE_METAL_PLATE

Co-polarization

Cross-polarization

CALIBRATION

**Strong reflection
on the metal plate**

**Multiple reflections
on wheels, plate
and Coyote**

The echo on the metallic plate is our reference echo at the time of the field test ($T = 17^{\circ}\text{C}$) for calibration of the data

LT_PROFILE_1

We expect the top cave echos to be around 70 ns delay on the radargram, but we are not sure to see it on this profiles.

Co-polarization

Cross-polarization

LT_INSIDE

LT_PROFILE_2

As on LT_PROFILE_1, We expect the top cave echos to be around 60-70 ns delay on the radargrams.

Co-polarization

Cross-polarization

LT_PROFILE_3

ONLY ONE 2 METERS PROFILE BEFORE RAIN

Co-polarization

Cross-polarization

LT_PROFILE_4

2 METERS PROFILE
DURING
DEMONSTRATION

Co-polarization

Cross-polarization

